

PRINCIPLES OF PREPARATION OF REPORTING ACCORDING TO INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS

¹Bozorova O.R., ²Kilicheva F.B.

¹Senior Lecturer at Educational University "Renaissance"

²Senior Lecturer at Educational University "Renaissance"

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Abstract. *The issues are considered being illustrated by structural and logical schemes, general tables and practical examples. The sequence of information presentation allows to understand the essence of international financial reporting standards, to develop practical skills of working with them.*

Keywords: *financial reporting, economics, to know, to be able, to own, international standards, information, principle, concept.*

Financial statements are prepared on a going concern basis unless management intends to liquidate the entity or cease operations or has no realistic alternative but to do so.

The application of functional currency is relevant for companies that have subsidiaries in different countries, which is why certain difficulties arise in choosing such a currency for presentation in the consolidated financial statements of the Group. For the purposes of preparing statements under US GAAP, choosing a functional currency is a simpler procedure that is not tied to the currency of the country and is calculated based on the currency in which the company incurs its main expenses and receives income. When applying IFRS, the requirements for functional currency are more complex and depend on the currency of the country in which the subsidiary operates. [3]

The purpose of financial reporting is to provide a fair presentation of information about the financial position, financial performance and cash flow of a company, useful to a wide range of users when making economic decisions. In connection with the introduction of international financial reporting standards into the legal sphere of our country, many organizations have questions about the need for their application in practice, as well as about the mechanisms for implementing and preparing reports according to international standards.

As a result of mastering the discipline, the student should:

know:

- the main trends determining the development of accounting and reporting in the Republic in connection with the transition to international financial reporting standards;
- the provisions of conceptual documents of international financial reporting standards;
- a summary and basic rules for the application of current international standards;
- methods of disclosing information in reporting;

be able to:

- freely navigate the rules for applying the most important theoretical provisions and principles - international financial reporting standards in practice;
- logically correctly express and justify ones point of view on topics related to international financial reporting standards;

- operate with concepts and categories of international financial reporting standards;
- independently apply international standards when preparing financial statements;

possess:

- practical skills in applying international financial reporting standards and performing the necessary calculations;
- skills in making professional decisions in the process of selecting the best options for accounting methods and reporting;
- skills in preparing all types of reports in accordance with international financial reporting standards and drafting explanatory notes taking into account international disclosure requirements[4]

The information in financial statements must fairly represent transactions and other events, so it is necessary that they are accounted for and presented in accordance with their essence and economic reality, and not just their legal form.

The essence of transactions and other events does not always correspond to what follows from their legal form.

Example: Sale at a price different from fair value.

If assets are sold at a price below or above their fair value, it is likely that there is a related transaction that explains the reason for the sale.

If the sale price is above fair value, it is almost certainly a disguised loan with future transactions to ensure its repayment.

Qualitative characteristics of reporting under – international financial reporting standards.

Presentation. 1. Understandability:

- sufficient knowledge of users in the field of business and commercial activities;
- complexity for understanding is not an argument for excluding information from the reporting.

2. Comparability:

- different periods (comparable data for the previous period);
- different companies (main provisions of the Accounting Policy);
- consistent approach to assessing and reflecting financial results

Content. 1. Relevance (for users to make decisions):

- balance between timeliness and reliability;
- costs of providing information should not exceed benefits derived from the information.

2. Materiality (information is material if its omission or distortion could influence the economic decisions of users)

Reliability. 1. Reliability of provision (compliance with recognition criteria).

2. Priority of content over form.

3. Neutrality.

4. Prudence.

5. Completeness (relationship with materiality and costs/benefits)

If the price is below fair value, then perhaps the essence of the transaction is a desire to defer recognition of the gain on the sale by understating a future expense item. For example, a company "sells" equipment to a third party at a price below fair value. In this case, a leaseback agreement is entered into for the equipment, and the rent is set below commercial rates. As a result,

the profit not received on the sale will be returned in subsequent periods, and this is nothing more than a form of profit smoothing.

Example: Combining transactions. Inventory may be “sold” to a third party on the condition that the seller retains the right to repurchase it at a future date, often at a pre-agreed price that is calculated to provide the buyer with, in effect, a consideration for the loan. When all the “related” transactions are considered together, it becomes clear that this is in fact a financing transaction, which should be reflected in the accounting.

Financial statements under – International Financial Reporting Standards should be prepared on the basis of the fundamental assumptions defined in the “Principles for the Preparation and Presentation of Financial Statements under – International Financial Reporting Standards”[5].

The going concern assumption means that the company will continue in business for the foreseeable future and, in addition to that intention, it must have the economic ability to continue in business.

The financial statements are prepared on a going concern basis unless management intends to liquidate the company or cease operations or has no realistic alternative but to do so.

Accrual accounting – companies must prepare their financial statements, except for cash flow information, on an accrual basis.

Accrual accounting requires that economic events be recognized and reported in the period in which they occur, regardless of whether cash is paid or received.

The principles for preparing and presenting financial statements under – “International Financial Reporting Standards” define five basic elements of financial statements:

- assets;
- liabilities;
- income;
- expenses;
- capital.

An asset is a resource controlled by a company as a result of past events, from which an increase in economic benefits is expected in the future.

More important in the first part of the definition of assets is the concept of control. It characterizes, first of all, the ability of a company to receive benefits from the use of specific resources or to limit the rights of other persons to receive these benefits.

Control is usually supported by legal ownership or actual possession of the asset, but this is not the determining factor. Assets recognized in accounting must arise as a result of past events (transactions). As a rule, such events are the acquisition of assets for cash, on credit or by barter, the sale of goods or services, the conclusion of agreements to receive some economic benefits in the future.

Future economic benefits are expressed in the ability of an asset to contribute to an increase in the company's net cash inflows.

A liability is a present obligation of the company that has arisen as a result of past events, the settlement of which will result in a decrease in economic benefits.

A present obligation, by definition, arises as a result of past events, called obligating events.

Obligating events are those that result in the company having no alternative but to perform the obligation.

Equity is the portion of the assets remaining in a company after all its liabilities have been paid off.

Income is an increase in economic benefits resulting from an increase in assets or a decrease in liabilities, resulting in an increase in equity not related to member contributions.

Thus, by definition, income is not only revenue, but also other profits reflected in the statement of comprehensive income or accounted for in the equity section (for example, revaluation of fixed assets and intangible assets).

An expense is a reduction in economic benefits, in the form of an outflow of assets or an increase in liabilities, that results in a decrease in equity not attributable to shareholders.

An entity may experience an "outflow of economic benefits" due to the creation of a new asset. In such situations, it is important to determine whether the asset meets the definition of an asset for it to be recognised in the statement of financial position and, if not, whether the cost should be recognised as an expense in the period in which it is incurred.

Recognition criteria are the conditions that must be met before an element of the financial statements can be included in the financial statements.

There are three criteria for recognizing elements of financial statements:

- compliance with the definition of an element of financial statements;
 - the probability that future economic benefits associated with a particular element of financial statements will be received or lost;
 - the ability to measure or estimate reliably the cost of an element of financial statements.
- various bases are used for measurement purposes:
- historical cost is the amount paid to acquire assets or received in exchange for a liability;
 - fair value is the amount that would be received to sell an asset or paid to transfer a liability in an orderly transaction between market participants on the measurement date (for more details, see - International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) "Fair Value Measurement");
 - discounted (present) value is the amount of future cash flows associated with an asset or liability, adjusted for the time value of money (discount factor).

Market approach: fair value is the price that would be obtained from market transactions for identical or comparable (i.e. similar) assets and liabilities.

Cost approach: fair value is the amount that would be required currently to replace the productive capacity of an asset (i.e. current replacement cost).

3. Income approach: fair value is the discounted amount of future cash flows associated with an asset or liability.

Valuation techniques used to estimate fair value should be applied consistently.

However, changes in valuation techniques are required in the following cases:

- if new markets develop;
- new information becomes available; - previously used information is no longer available;
- valuation techniques are improved; - market conditions change.

Changes resulting from a change in valuation technique are reflected as a change in accounting estimate (in accordance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IAS)).

Hierarchy of inputs for fair value measurement.

There are 3 levels of hierarchy: the highest priority is Level 1 inputs and the lowest priority is Level 3 inputs.

Level 1 is quoted prices (unadjusted) in active markets for identical assets or liabilities at the measurement date (e.g. for quoted financial assets and liabilities).

Level 2 is inputs that are not quoted prices included in Level 1 and that are directly or indirectly observable for the asset or liability, such as:

- quoted prices for similar assets or liabilities in active markets;
- inputs, other than quoted prices, that are observable for the asset or liability (e.g., interest rates and yield curves observable in the market).

Adjustments to Level 2 inputs vary based on factors specific to the asset or liability (e.g., the condition or location of the asset).

Level 3 inputs are unobservable for the asset or liability (e.g., the entity's financial forecast, the discounted amount of cash flows associated with the asset or liability).

Statutory statements:

- Statement of financial position;
- Statement of comprehensive income;
- Statement of changes in equity;
- Statement of Cash Flows;
- Notes, consisting of a brief overview of significant accounting policies and other explanatory information;

– a statement of financial position as of the beginning of the earliest period presented (if the company makes a retrospective change in an accounting policy, changes previously reported information, or reclassifies items in the financial statements).

Additional statements (other information). Many companies, in addition to the financial statements, present management's financial reviews, which describe and explain the key features of the company's financial performance, its financial position, and the principal uncertainties it faces.

Financial statements must be clearly identified and distinguished from other information within the same published document (for example, an annual report or prospectus) [7].

International Financial Reporting Standards apply only to financial statements, and not to other information presented in an annual report or other document.

According to International Financial Reporting Standards (IAS), it is not a change in accounting policy:

- the adoption of a new accounting policy for events or transactions that have not occurred previously or are not material;
- the adoption of an accounting policy for events or transactions that differ in substance from previously occurring events and transactions.

Because of the uncertainties inherent in business, many financial statement items cannot be measured precisely but can only be estimated.

A change in an accounting estimate is a revision of an accounting estimate as a result of new information, experience, or subsequent events.

A prospective method is used to reflect changes in accounting estimates. The effect of a change in an accounting estimate should be included in the calculation of net profit or loss:

- in the period in which the change occurs, if it affects only that period;
- in the period in which the change occurs and in future periods, if it affects both.

Examples of changes in accounting estimates:

- a change in the estimate of doubtful accounts;
- a change in the useful lives of depreciable assets;
- a change in the depreciation method;
- a change in the estimate of obsolescence of inventories.

The effects of changes in accounting estimates shall be included in the same line items in the statement of comprehensive income in which the estimates were previously included.

An entity shall correct material prior period errors retrospectively in the first set of financial statements authorized for issue after their discovery by:

- restating the comparative amounts for the prior period(s) presented in which the error occurred;
- or when the error occurred before the earliest period presented, by restating the opening balances of assets, liabilities and equity for the earliest prior period presented.

Thus, items affecting the current and future periods need to be adjusted in the period in which they are discovered, but there is no need to disclose these events in the financial statements.

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